

The Need For The Establishment Of Automated Library System In Bayelsa State College Of Education

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ABSTRACT

The study looked at the need for the establishment of automated library system in Bayelsa State college of education. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 30 library staff in selected tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The study developed a questionnaire instrument titled "The need for the establishment of Automated Library Systems" (TNEALS). The data obtained from the study was analyzed using simple mean. Pilot study was conducted with 15 librarians in various tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The findings obtained from the study showed that automated library is not used for educational consultancies, automated library is not used for seminars, automated library is not well equipped for public consumption and automated library is not frequently visited based on standard operations and public recommendations. Also, another findings revealed that that students do not use the automated library on daily basis, students do not use the automated library for research, many students complain on the shortage of library resources in campus and many students do have access to many advance library materials. Additional findings show that lecturers do not use the automated library often, lecturers do not carry extensive research in school library, lecturers are not exposed to advance academic materials in the library and lecturers do not recommend campus library to colleagues in other institutions. Further Findings revealed that there is no significant correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: Need, Establishment, Automated Library, System

INTRODUCTION

Library automation refers to use of computers in library work including services computers were engaged in library service in USA in 1950s in a very modest way. Dr H P Luhn had organized computerized indexes in 1950s computers entered and found some place in American library during this decade. However, their use and application was very limited and restricted due to the high cost of hardware and non-availability of application software packages.

During 1960s the cost of hardware came down and appreciable attempts were made towards developing library application packages. This led to increased use of computers in library and printing industries. In

April 1960 the American Chemical Society published its chemical titles through computers. In this decade, one of the most significant developments in this direction was seen in MARC I. In the year 1963 W K Gilbert prepared a report on computerization of Library of congress (Abdullahi and Saka, 2016);. On the basis of this report the MARC I project was initiated in 1966, and the work of bringing out the Library of congress catalogue in machine-readable catalogue (MARC) form was started and completed. There was a heartening welcome of the tape containing the catalogue. MEDLARS and INTREX projects are similar examples of producing machine-readable catalogues. Nowadays computers have become almost essential components of library work in developing countries (Aboh and Yusuf, 2020). The Indian statistical institute, Calcutta was the first in India to install a computer system in 1955, and to develop an indigenous computer in 1964. In India computers were used in library work for the first time possibly by INSDOC by bringing out the roster of Indian scientific and technical translators with the help of computers (Okebukola, 2012). INSDOC brought out the first union scientific and technical translators with the title regional union catalogue of scientific serials, Bombay Poona in 1973. In 1978 INSDOC initiated SDI service as a NISSAT project with chemical Abstracts and INSPEC databases, with the use of CAN/SDI software of IIT, madras, in 1970's many library ventured in preparing computerized databases. Through the initiative and financial support of NISSAT many library networks was initiated and are operative. Notable of these networks are CALIBNET (Calcutta library network) DELNET (Delhi libraries network) INFLIBNET (information and library network) PUNENET (Pune library network) etc. Some other notable networks are NICNET, INDONET, SERNET, ERNET etc. Nowadays, many institutions such as DRTC, INSDOC, DESIDOC, NISSAT etc are engaged in imparting training for computer application in library work through regular sponsored and part time courses. The price of computer hardware and software has come down considerably. Owing to these factors computers have become popular with Indian libraries.

The library plays a critical role in our society it is an important component of any educational institution, which is hub of the teaching and learning activities where students, researchers and teachers can explore the vast resources of information. In the age of information communication technology computers are being used for day- to-day housekeeping activity of the library which saves the time of the library service smooth and effective. In the age of ICT library scenario has been drastically changed in terms of collection, organization and services. Simultaneously user's demands and attitudes have changed in its kinds. Also the information seeking behaviour of user has dynamically changed. They want relevant authentic information very quickly within a single place at their hand. This concept has posed challenges for library professionals for quick delivery of library services and information. This development in library field has brought the ideas of library automation. Library automation is inevitable in this age of information and information technologies. Library automation is the use of automatic and semi automation data processing machines to perform such traditional activities as acquisition cataloguing and circulation. Library automation may thus be distinguished from related fields such as information retrieval automatic indexing and abstracting and automatic textual analysis.

Information explosion has resulted in the production of a large amount of literatures in every field of knowledge. Accordingly the print documents are coming to the library in huge numbers which is not possible for a library to manage the collection manually. Now a day's no user has time to search the required and relevant information from dense heap of information collection. They have no time to go shelve by shelve to pick up a book. So it necessitated for library automation. In most of libraries are yet to be automated (Ogunla and Akanmu Adeyemo, 2010).

Library services require a series of works like acquiring, preparing and organising documents of different types and available in many formats. The activities related to acquisition of documents, technical processing of acquired documents, circulation and maintenance of processed documents are known as housekeeping operations. In a traditional library system (managed manually) these time consuming, labour intensive activities and routine clerical chores are performed slowly and expensively by library staff. Libraries all over the world, right from 1970s (with the advent of Personal Computer) are increasingly attempting to automate some of these activities for minimising human clerical routines and

thereby optimising productivity and creativity of library staff. Library automation is the generic term that denotes applications of Information Communications Technologies (ICT) for performing manual operations in libraries of any type or size.

Statement of the Problem

The library system in Nigeria for long has been operating using the analogue system. This has discouraged a lot of uses especially students. There is the need to upgrade our library system to the global standards for automated libraries. Despite the early adoption of automation in Nigerian libraries, many libraries in Nigeria at yet to be automated. For example, Ogunrombi (2015) reported that most tertiary institutions that automate their library in 1983 using APPLE II are suffering a major setback currently. In spite of various setbacks and experiences by libraries in Nigeria, some libraries still recorded success in their automation projects. For instance, Otunla and Akanmu Adeyemo (2010) recounted automation process of Bowen University Library, Iwo and explained that as a result of automation, library operation and provision of information services are enhanced and images of Librarians boosted.

Purpose of the Study

The study is aimed at finding out the state of automated libraries in college of Education in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the level of utilization of automated libraries facility in college of Education in Bayelsa State.
2. Find out the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by students in college of Education in Bayelsa State.
3. Find out the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff in college of Education in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were adopted for the study:

1. What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility in college of Education in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by students in college of Education in Bayelsa State?
3. What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff in college of Education in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance and used for the study:

1. There is no significant correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State.

Scope of the study

The work is limited to the need for the establishment of automated library system in Bayelsa State College of education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Traditional, Automated and Digital: Three Eras of Library Systems

The application of ICT tools in the form of hardware, software and network changed conventional library system considerably right from 1970s. Now, we have an array of modern information handling systems named as computerized library system, automated library system, electronic library system, digital library system and virtual library system. However, we are going to restrict discussion to two stable modern library systems – automated library system and digital library system. You already know what an automated library system is. Now question comes what is a digital library system and how does it differ from automated library system? Digital libraries are major application entities of Internet and Web technologies. These are considered as next generation library services. In simple words, Digital libraries are managed collections of digital objects. These entities enable the creation, organisation, maintenance,

management, access to, sharing and preservation of digital knowledge bearing objects or document collections. Digital libraries are being created today by many institutes and agencies for different target groups and in diverse fields like agriculture, cultural heritage, education, health, governance, science, social sciences, social development, etc. In its final shape a digital library system will be a single window federated search interface for a diverse range of information resources collected or optimized by a library system.

Availability of free/libre open source software (FLOSS) based digital library software packages, application of open standards and sharing of domain knowledge through Wiki, Blogs etc. help in designing Digital libraries even in developing block of the world. Now the question comes that what are the advantages of digital libraries? There are some obvious benefits of Digital libraries over the automated library systems. Some of the key benefits of digital libraries are:

- Traditional libraries are associated with the organization and provision of access to physical material like print-on-paper publications.
- Automated library systems are providing improved access to their collections but online access facilities are limited to the computerized library catalogue (OPAC).
- Digital libraries differ significantly from such libraries because these entities facilitate online access to and work with digital versions of full text resources in multimedia-driven environment. Library automation activities address two major issues – library housekeeping operations and access to library resources. An automated library system has cataloguing data in digital format but source documents are mostly available in print formats. In a digital library setup both metadata (document description data) and documents are available in digital format.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. This design was selected as questionnaire items were administered directly to respondents in the field. The response items were retrieved after the respondents were given appropriate answers based on their opinions.

Population of the Study

The study used a population of 30 library staff in selected tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The figure was obtained from the chief librarian in various Polytechnic in Bayelsa State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

There was no need for sampling as the size of the population is so small. Therefore, the entire population of thirty (30) senior library staff was adopted as sample for the study.

Validation of Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face validation by an expert in Library and Information Science in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The expert checked the language content of the questionnaires before it was sent to the field.

Instrument for the Study

The study developed an instrument titled “The need for the establishment of Automated Library Systems” (TNEALS). The instrument is a four point rating scale consisting of Strongly Agree, (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response options were weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument consists of a total of twenty (20) items.

Reliability of Instrument

The study used the test- retest method to obtain the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 3 senior library staff in Rivers State Polytechnic to fill. After two weeks, the same instrument was administered to the same set of respondents. The data obtained from the instrument was calculated using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient to obtain a reliability value of 0.87. This was considered adequate for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data obtained from the study was analyzed using simple mean, charts and Pearson moment correlation coefficient.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One

What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility in college of education in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Level of utilization of automated libraries facility in college of education in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
1.	The automated library is not used for educational Consultancies.	3.44	Accept
2.	The automated library is not used for seminars.	3.56	Accept
3.	The automated library is not well equipped for Public consumption.	3.55	Accept
4.	The automated library is not frequently visited Based on standard operations and public Recommendations.	3.56	Accept

The findings revealed in research question 1, table 1 showed that items 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. This implies that automated library is not used for educational consultancies, automated library is not used for seminars, automated library is not well equipped for public consumption and automated library is not frequently visited based on standard operations and public recommendations.

Research Question Two

What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by students in college of Education in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Level of utilization of automated libraries facility by students in college of Education in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
5.	Students do not use the automated library on Daily basis	3.22	Accept
6.	Students do not use the automated library for Research.	3.56	Accept
7.	Many students complain on the shortage of Library resources in campus.	3.45	Accept
8.	Many students do have access to many advance Library materials.	3.67	Accept

The findings revealed in research question 2, table 2 showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 were all accepted to the various questions. This implies that students do not use the automated library on daily basis, students do not use the automated library for research, many students complain on the shortage of library resources in campus and many students do have access to many advance library materials.

Research Question Three: *What is the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff in college of Education in Bayelsa State?*

Table 3: Level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff in college of Education in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
9.	Lecturers do not use the automated library Often.	3.22	Agree
10.	Lecturers do not carry extensive research in school library	3.14	Agree
11.	Lecturers are not exposed to advance academic materials in the library	3.78	Agree
12.	Lecturers do not recommend campus library to Colleagues in other institutions.	3.64	Agree

The findings revealed in research question 3, table 3 showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 all agreed to the fact that lecturers do not use the automated library often, lecturers do not carry extensive research in

school library, lecturers are not exposed to advance academic materials in the library and lecturers do not recommend campus library to colleagues in other institutions.

Hypotheses

There is no significant correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State

S/N	X (Academic Staff)	Y (Students)	X ²	Y ²	XY
1.	3.22	3.22	10.37	10.37	10.37
2.	3.14	3.56	9.56	12.67	11.18
3.	3.78	3.45	14.29	11.90	13.04
4.	3.64	3.67	13.25	13.47	13.36
Σ	13.78	13.90	47.47	48.41	47.95

R-calculated value is 0.20.

This implies that r-calculated value of 0.20 is less than r-tabulated value of 0.878 at 0.05 level of significant. This signifies that the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, it would be stated that there is no significant correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings obtained from the study showed that automated library is not used for educational consultancies, automated library is not used for seminars, automated library is not well equipped for public consumption and automated library is not frequently visited based on standard operations and public recommendations. This is in line with the opinion of Abdullahi & Saka, (2016) that said that most institution does not well equipped library facilities.

Also, another findings revealed that that students do not use the automated library on daily basis, students do not use the automated library for research, many students complain on the shortage of library resources in campus and many students do have access to many advance library materials. According to Aina, (2013) most students lack interest in visiting the library mainly due to poor facilities.

Additional findings show that lecturers do not use the automated library often, lecturers do not carry extensive research in school library, lecturers are not exposed to advance academic materials in the library and lecturers do not recommend campus library to colleagues in other institutions. Arko-Cobbah (2004) observed that most lecturers do not use the library resources as a basis for research.

Further Findings revealed that there is no significant correlation between the level of utilization of automated libraries facility by academic staff and students in college of Education in Bayelsa State. Bashorun, Ifeoluwa & Fumilayo, (2019) emphasized that both student lecturers share the same opinion on the poor state library resources in Bayelsa State.

CONCLUSION

The findings obtained from the study showed that the automated library is not well equipped with modern library resources. Also, most lecturers and students do not use library resources mainly due the poor state of the facility.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was finally recommended that:

1. Government should fund the library system in college of Education in Bayelsa State.
2. The educational institutions should apply to various educational fund raising organizations to supply and provide advanced digital resources in college library.

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